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CONTENTS

Issue 1

TOURIST ATTRACTIONS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF LOKOJA, NIGERIA	1-16
<i>Adeniyi, Enekole Esther</i>	
THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANT OF ACCESS TO INFORMAL DOMESTIC WATER SUPPLY IN IJEBU-ODE, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA	17-31
<i>OBISANYA, D. Damola, ONAFESO, D., Olumide, and BADEJO, A. Bamidele</i>	
ASSESSING TRENDS IN AGRICULTURAL EXPANSION, VEGETATION RECOVERY, AND LANDSCAPE STABILISATION IN SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA (1984 -2024)	32-44
<i>Abdulumumin Garba Budah, Sunday Olukayode Oladejo, Fakpor Akpofure Miller, and Micheal Ajide Oyinloye</i>	
KNOWLEDGE OF ROAD SIGNS AND COMPLIANCE OF INTRA-URBAN COMMERCIAL BUS DRIVERS WITH TRAFFIC REGULATIONS IN ILORIN, NIGERIA	45-57
<i>Shittu F.M, Usman B. A, and Abdul, M.</i>	
PLANT SPECIES FREQUENCY, ABUNDANCE AND FOREST DYNAMICS IN CENTRAL ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA	58-68
<i>Adamu Sanusi., Abel Aderemi Adebayo., Gidado Abdulrazaq, and Musa Abdulkadir</i>	
ECOSYSTEM SERVICES OF JIKWATHLAR SPRING AREA OF GARKIDA TAULA CATCHMENT, BIU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA	69-86
<i>Rejoice Paul Mbaya, Nwaune Lawrence Ukoje, and Hadiza Abubakar Monguno</i>	
IMPACT OF PUBLIC TRANSPORTATION QUALITY ON PASSENGERS' SATISFACTION IN THE BENIN METROPOLIS, NIGERIA	87-104
<i>Atewe, Amasikomwan Festus</i>	

Issue 2

SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES (LULCC) IN EFON LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EKITI STATE, NIGERIA 105-118

Idowu Adewale OGUNLADE

ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNITY-BASED WASTE MANAGEMENT METHODS IN AKOKO SOUTH WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF ONDO STATE, NIGERIA 119-133

Agede, A. A, Ogunbodede, E. F. and Ogunade, A. O.

SMALLHOLDER FARMERS' ACCESS TO CLIMATE CHANGE INFORMATION IN THE NIGER DELTA 134-142

Prof. Onovughe Ikelegbe and Dr Joshua Longe

URBAN ROADSIDE TOPSOIL–SUBSOIL NUTRIENTS UNDER THE CANOPY OF *TERMINALIA MANTALY*: RELATIONSHIPS AMONG TREE GROWTH, BIOMASS, AND SOIL QUALITY INDICATORS 143-161

Paul Orobosa Orobator and Solomon Eghosa Uhunamure

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF FREIGHT FORWARDERS AS DETERMINANTS OF COMPLIANCE WITH TRADE FACILITATION POLICIES IN NIGERIA 162-182

Ademola Benson Irinyemi and Adeyinka Peter Ajayi

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF LAND USE/LAND COVER CHANGES ON GULLY ERODED LANDSCAPE IN GOMBE METROPOLIS, GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA 183-198

Richard Sunday Thlakm, Jajere Abubakar Ahmed and Umar Yahaya Zakarai

GEO-STUDIES FORUM

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ECOSYSTEM SERVICES OF JIKWATHLAR SPRING AREA OF GARKIDA TAULA CATCHMENT, BIU LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, BORNO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The Jikwathlar Spring ecosystem is located within the Garkida Taula Catchment, Biu Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria. The spring is deeply integrated into the cultural and ecological life of the Garkida community, serving as a spiritual, hydrological, and biodiversity resource. The study examined the tangible and intangible ecosystem services derived from this sacred spring environment and documented how indigenous knowledge and conservation practices have maintained ecological integrity and supported community livelihoods over decades. The study combined ecological field surveys with ethnographic methods such as Key Informant Interviews (KII) with community elders, women, youth and with custodians of the spring and the traditional leaders. Direct field observation, spatial mapping of land cover features around the spring and thematic classification of services using the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment framework were also integrated to acquire the needed data and information for identification and categorization of ecosystem services. The results revealed that the spring provides various ecosystem services including Provisioning Services like perennial water supply used for domestic use, irrigation, and livestock and medicinal resources, wild fruits and games. It also provides Regulating Services including vegetation and surface runoff control, tree microclimate stabilization and carbon sequestration. Other services are Cultural Services (sacred site embodying traditional spiritual beliefs and practices) and Supporting Services (supports biodiversity, including endemic bird species, insects, and diverse flora and various animal species). The findings suggest that this ecosystem represents an exemplary model of community-driven conservation that contributes to sustainable resource management and biodiversity protection. The study recommended the recognition of sacred natural sites in environmental legislation, and the support for local conservation efforts for sustainable livelihood and agro-ecological practices.*

Keywords: Ecosystem services, Jikwathlar Spring, Sacred ecology, cultural conservation, Indigenous knowledge

INTRODUCTION

An ecosystem is a complex network of living organisms (plants, animals, microorganisms) interacting with one another and their physical environment (air, water, soil) in a specific area and characterized by the flow of energy and cycling of nutrients and maintain ecological balance and biodiversity (Raven 2022).

Acreman, et al., (2011) noted that the springs in savannah ecosystems not only serve as critical ecological infrastructures but also support biodiversity, water regulation and nutrient cycling. The perennial or seasonal water sources derived from these springs provide consistent water supply in the dry environment of the savannah. It also sustains wildlife populations and enhances riparian

vegetation. Furthermore, water from springs supports microhabitats needed for the survival of mammals, amphibians and birds especially during dry season. The springs also recharge aquifers, moderate microclimate, and minimize wildfires risk from higher humidity in their immediate environments (Boulton, 2005). Other than the direct ecosystem services, springs also fosters water purification, carbon sequestration and have traditional or cultural importance like sacred sites and ecotourism. Spring also contributes to the general resilience of the landscape by serving as natural buffers against climate variability and anthropogenic impact. Spring can simultaneously sustain the livelihoods of the inhabitants and biodiversity, but subject to the sustainable and conservation. Therefore, it is important to integrate spring conservation into the management strategies of the savannah (Rassam et al., 2017) which can be achieved through researches of this nature

As important as the springs in savannah ecosystems are, there are clear research gaps in the awareness of the specific ecosystem services of the springs within the Nigerian savannah belt. For instance, most existing studies only focus on wetlands (Eric, et al., 2022; Makwinja, et al., 2024) or water resources (Cartwright & Johnson, 2018; Sieben & Kotze 2024) without a detailed investigation of springs as distinct ecological units. These gaps have led to inadequate data on the springs biodiversity and ecological functions, influence on seasonal dynamics, and their contributions to livelihoods. The effects of land use change on spring sustainability in the savannah region is also a gap which hinders sustainable conservation and integration of springs into land and water management strategies. Sacred natural springs like the Jikwathlar spring which is situated in a culturally significant volcanic landscape of

the Biu Plateau offers unique combination of spiritual, ecological, and livelihood functions. The Jikwathlar Spring is revered by the local Bura/Pabir people for its perennial water flow and spiritual power. The need to document and analyze such services is crucial for integrating local conservation models into broader ecological frameworks. This study therefore, documents the multiple ecological benefits derived from the spring by stock taking of the services provided by the Jikwathlar Spring in Garkida Taula Community in Biu LGA, Borno State, Nigeria. This will be of importance to ecologists, conservationists, policy makers, environmental scientist educators and nature lovers interested in ecosystem services.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept used for this study is the concept of the Social-Ecological Systems (SES). The SES framework reflects the co-evolution of both cultural and ecological components, where indigenous knowledge fosters a balance that sustains both the social and ecological aspects of the studied catchment. Historically, Indigenous communities maintained a harmonious relationship with their environment, supported by indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) and traditional authority structures (Chiwandamira, 2000). This framework analyzes the complex interactions between social and ecological components within a system, highlighting the role of social institutions and traditional governance in resource management and indigenous conservation efforts (Howard, et al., 2008).

This study investigated the characteristics within the social system and focused on the ecological aspects of the study area including natural resources, the ecosystem, biodiversity,

climate and environmental process. This involves assessing the environmental conditions, changes, and impacts within the ecological system. The world's biodiversity provides numerous benefits to society, commonly referred to as ecosystem services.

However, many of these services are at risk due to unsustainable human activities (Ash *et al* 2010 cited in Inter-governmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES 2018)). The Social Ecological Systems chart presented in Figure 1 shows how the components co-relates,

Figure 1: Concept of Social-Ecological System (SES)
Source: Adapted from Marten, 2001

Scholarly works on ecosystem services have grown significantly in recent decades, particularly with the contributions of the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005), which classifies ecosystem services into four key categories that support human well-being, all fundamentally supported by biodiversity. The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity (TEEB) is a global initiative focused on making nature's value visible, (TEEB for Agriculture & Food, 2021). This

ecosystem services are presented in the segmented pyramid diagram in Figure 2 showing how the Ecosystem represents sources of natural capital and provide services to the community. Both Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) and traditional conservation ethics are widely regarded by scientists and local communities as crucial for managing natural resources and maintaining ecosystem resilience within SES.

Figure 2: Ecosystem services segmented pyramid
Source: TEEBAgri Food (2021)

In African contexts, the integration of sacred groves and springs into conservation efforts has been studied by scholars like Gadgil et al. (1993) and Berkes (2008), where the importance of traditional ecological knowledge were emphasized. In northeastern Nigeria, studies by Maina et al. (2020) and Chah, (2022) have shown that sacred sites serve both ecological and cultural functions. However, there remains a gap in documenting site-specific services using participatory and ethnographic approaches, particularly for Borno State's sacred landscapes like Jikwathlar spring area.

THE STUDY AREA

The Jikwathlar Spring is located within the Garkida Taula sub-catchment of the Dambuwa watershed in Biu Local Government Area in Borno State. It is located within Latitude 10.629008 N and 12.344069 E (Figure. 3). The spring is located within the larger Dambuwa catchment which takes its

source from Biu Plateau and flows westward to Babalwada community where the river diverts southwards to join River Hawul in Hawul LGA. Dambuwa catchment lies between Latitudes 10°31'00" N and 10°42'00" N and Longitudes 12°09'00" E and 12°36'00" E. The catchment cuts across three LGAs all within Borno State: Askira Uba, Biu and Hawul and covers a total land area of 351.43 km². Major settlements within the catchment include Garkida Taula, Babalwada, in Biu LGA, Dalwa, Dambuwa, Nyamghar, Wawataku, Boza, and Gaska in Askira/Uba LGA. The Jikwathlar Spring's catchment itself has an area of 72.69km² with Garkida Taula as one of the settlements within the catchment. Larger parts of the catchment lie in Askira/Uba and Hawul LGA while the Biu Plateau part of the catchment lies in Hawul LGA.

Rainfall periods are from May to September. Mean annual rainfall is highest in August (295.18 mm) and about 196.88 mm in September. Mean monthly temperature in the spring is least in December with about 23.61°

C and highest in April (30. 67° C). Relative humidity is higher than 50% from May to October with the highest (87.18%) in August. The months of April and November generally have Relative humidity more than 40%.

Jikwathlar Spring is located in the Sudan Savannah zone of North-eastern Nigeria (Mbaya, 2025). The study area is at the foot of the Mandaragirau volcanic outcrop and is characterized mainly with basaltic rocks (Abdullahi, 2015).

Figure 3: The Study Area
 Source: Extracted from SRTM DEM data (2011): Research work (2024)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reconnaissance survey was conducted in April 2024 to explore the research context, identify key issues and classify research questions. This facilitated the design of the sampling and type of data collection strategies. Due to ethical concerns therefore, prior informed consent of the Village Head (Bulama) was sought for approval to undertake the field research and permission to conduct Key Informants Interview (including Historical Comparison Interview). The age group of 60years old and above was selected for the Historical Comparison respondents based on (Ugwu & Ene, 2023). The environmental history provided valuable insights into past environmental conditions and helped better understand management practices and environmental drivers that may have negatively impacted the area.

Field work with the help of field assistants was conducted and observation of natural resources around the area was carried out. Specie list of the plants and animals found in the study site were documented. Photographs were taken to show the environment and other related features within the study area. Identifications of the ecosystem services was carried out through physical observation and identification. KII comprised of community

elders, women, youth and with custodians of the spring and the traditional leaders and custodians of the Spring. The study also considered some historical comparison questions about the practices in the area to explain changes in practices, and in the process. The secondary data for the study were obtained from relevant published materials such as journal articles, documented reports, publications and internet sources.

The data, being qualitative data were analyzed using the following steps: The first is data preparation and organization or data cleaning by ensuring that the format is suitable for the analysis. Secondly, the data were coded or labels to the desired themes or categories. Categorization was the next step which involves group-coded data into categories or sub-themes. The last step includes data interpretation by interpreting the findings, and for the patterns or relationships among the data set. The results are presented in tables, while the captured pictures were also displayed accordingly.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION ECOSYSTEM SERVICES IN JIKWATHLAR SPRING AREA

The different categories of the ecosystem services provided are presented in Table 1

Table 1: Categories of ecosystem services in Jikwathlar Spring area

Categories	Services
Provisioning	i. Provision of medicinal plants and herbs
	ii. Water Supply for diverse uses including domestic use and for medication
	iii. Home for different animals
Regulating	i. Site for natural vegetation decomposition (trees and leaves)
	ii. Environment with conducive Microclimate
	iii. Protection by the spirits regulates the kind of activities around the place
	iv. Soil nutrient regulation
Cultural	i. Reduces peoples' level of stress and tension
	ii. Psychologically refreshing environment
	iii. Sacred ground for sacrifices
	iv. Favour with and from neighbouring communities
	v. The spirits are preserving the area and the community at large
	vi. Natural landscape
	vii. Indigenous Knowledge center due to the cultural beliefs and practices
	viii. Sacred site that connects humans to realm of the spirits.
Supporting	i. Fertile and conducive surrounding for gardening and irrigation activities
	ii. Ecosystem with wide range of biodiversity
	iii. Nutrient cycling due to natural decomposition of plants

Source: Authors' Fieldwork 2024

The four main categories of ecological services (provisional, regulating, cultural and supporting) are all present in Jikwathlar Spring area as well as the existing services of each of the ecological services. Cultural services recorded the highest number of services among the four categories of the ecological services. This finding shows the importance of Jikwathlar Spring as a cultural ecological service.

PROVISIONING SERVICES:

Provisional services especially medicinal and water supply for domestic purposes which are derive from the spring are very essential to the

rural dwellers of Jikwathlar Spring area. The medicinal benefits of some of the available plants in the spring area are presented in Table 2. Garkida Taula people use different species of plants around the spring to take care of several health issues, some plants have multiple uses. Most of the residents in the community and the surrounding communities rely so much on these plants to cure diseases and ailments. Diverse methods are being used in the preparation and administration of the local medicines obtained from the area, by boiling, drying and grinding into powder, chewing or soaking in water and then taken separately or by adding to food or water.

Table 2: Some medicinal plants in the Jikwathlar Spring area

Local Names of plants (Bura)	Name of plant in English	Botanical Names	Parts used	Medicinal Purposes
Fumwa	Shea Butter tree	<i>Vitellaria paradoxa</i>	Bark, fruits seeds (nuts)	All-round medicine: pain relief, treatment of wound etc
Debiro	Frankincense	<i>Boswellia hutch</i>	Bark	For pregnant women, treatment of wound, Snake bite, ulcer etc
Mangola	Mango	<i>Manginifera indica</i>	leaves, fruits	All forms of malaria
Kuvila	Gum Arabic	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	Pod, seed, bark	Stomach pain and for maganin rana
Surah	Chew Stick	<i>Anogeissus leiocarpus</i>	Bark (Bwatila)	Cough and fever for children
Dikir	Mahogany	<i>Khaya senegalenses</i>	Bark	Stomach pain, Ear drop
Kamda	Fig	<i>Ficus carica</i>	Bark, fruits	Skin diseases
Nina	Mistletoe	<i>Agelanthus dodoneifolius</i>	Leaves	Joining fractured bones
*Kurgilang	-	-	Root	Stomach pain, waist pain
*Dzinka	-	-	Bark	Measles, Ulcer, wound, (Akawa)
*Mbaksha	-	-	Root	Generally, for children
*Kutila	-	-	Root	Spiritual instructions

*No available English and botanical names

Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2024

The survey of medicinal plants around Jikwathlar Spring (Table 2) highlights the deep ethnobotanical knowledge embedded within local communities, particularly among the Bura people of Borno State. The identified taxa encompass widely known as medicinal species such as *Vitellaria paradoxa* (Shea butter tree), used extensively in West Africa for wound healing, pain relief, and dermatological applications (Maranz et al., 2004), and *Mangifera indica* (Mango), whose

leaves and fruits are traditionally employed in the treatment of malaria and related febrile illnesses (Akinmoladun et al., 2020). Other notable plants include *Boswellia hutch*, valued for its bark in treating snakebites, ulcers, and pregnancy-related conditions, and *Acacia nilotica*, commonly used for gastrointestinal disorders and “maganin rana” (heat-related ailments). Additionally, species such as *Anogeissus leiocarpus* (chew stick) and *Khaya senegalensis* (mahogany) are recorded

for their roles in pediatric cough, fever, and ear infections, underscoring their importance in primary healthcare delivery. Interestingly, some entries remain unidentified botanically (Kurgilang, Dzinka, Mbaksha, Kutila), yet they are linked to culturally significant uses ranging from child health to spiritual instructions, reflecting the intersection of medicinal and socio-cultural practices. This inventory highlights the conservation importance of Jikwathlar Spring as a reservoir of biodiversity and indigenous pharmacopeia, reinforcing the call for further phytochemical validation and sustainable management of these medicinal resources.

The indigenous knowledge on medicinal plants has seriously led to the adoption of medicinal plants harvesting methods that are not only sustainable but environmentally friendly. According to KII 2 respondent,

“the plants are still very much available. If the bark of a tree is required for instance, the trees will not be cut down but are carefully scooped in such a way that it does not affect the trunk or the entire tree (Plate 1), and in also in a quantity that is only enough for the treatment.”

Plate 1: Newly scooped out portion of the bark of a Mahogany tree for medicinal purpose
Source: Authors' Fieldwork, 2024

Other than the medicinal plants, the spring environment is also believed to be a natural healing place as the Village Head in a KII, revealed, that *“the Spring environment being a sacred place, cures ailment and heals on its own”*. The residents of the area see the spring and its surroundings as a home to spirits that

protects and inflict punishments on anyone who defaults on the instructions given by the spirits on the beliefs. For instance, a woman during the KII buttressed the spirituality of the spring that:

“It has helped us the residents because not only do the plants heal, the water does and the spring on its own, also heals. It gives instructions. The spirits in the area can talk and can be heard but cannot be seen.”

area for healing was healed immediately she stepped in the spring. One of the eldest women in the village also said: *“women give birth at home here, we don’t go to hospitals we depend on the spirits in the spring for help”*

Buttressing the spirituality of the spring and its environs, the Village Head narrated how a girl from Chimba village recently brought to the

Various species of animals were also identified around the Jikwathlar spring area, these are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Animal species identified around the Jikwathlar Spring

S/N	English name	Scientific name	Bura name	Hausa name
1.	Crocodiles	<i>Crocodylidae</i>	Nglim	Kada
2.	Tortoises	<i>Testudinidae</i>	Cima	Kunkuru
3.	Frogs	<i>Rana temporaria</i>	Whomba	Kwado
4.	Snakes	<i>Serpentes</i>	Pwapu	Maciji
5.	Lizards	<i>Agama</i>	Tawula	Kadangare
6.	Monitor Lizards	<i>Veranus</i>	Ngwalahu	Damo
7.	Giant Rats	<i>Cricetomys gambianus</i>	Mbekel	Gafiya
8.	Rats	<i>Rattus</i>	Kilan	Bera
9.	Duck	<i>Anas platyrhynchos</i>	Handa	Agwagwa
10.	Cat fish	<i>Clarias lazera</i>	Shular	Tarwada
11.	Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Baka	Karpasa
12.	Monkeys	Cercopithecidae	Chandim	Biri
13.	Birds	Aves	Adir	Tsuntsu
14.	Guinea Fowl	<i>Numida meleagris</i>	Tsevir	Zabo
15.	Snails	<i>Gastropoda</i>	Muhyetu	Dodon kwodi
16.	Bees	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	Chirmema	Kudan zuma
17.	Flies	<i>Musca domestica Linnaeus</i>	Chiri	Kuda
18.	Grasshoppers of diverse species		Hawa such as: Abilanggama Akwapthlahu Adzikal Angekduku Maturatu and Didambula	Fara

Source: Authors’ Fieldwork, 2024

These animals however, are neither hunted nor touched as part of the beliefs governing the practice on wild life conservation which forbids the killing of animals found around the sacred area. The species inventory from Jikwathlar Spring (Table 3) documents a

taxonomically broad assemblage ranging from large aquatic predators (crocodiles, *Crocodylidae*) and piscivores (catfish *Clarias* spp., Nile tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*) to semi-aquatic reptiles (monitor lizards), amphibians (frogs), invertebrates (snails,

bees, flies, grasshoppers) and a suite of small mammals and birds indicating that the spring and its riparian zone function as a multi-habitat refuge with both aquatic and terrestrial linkages. The recorded presence of large-bodied taxa (crocodiles and monitor lizards) suggests relatively intact riparian habitat or at least remnants capable of supporting higher trophic levels, while the presence of widely distributed, resilient fishes such as *O. niloticus* and *Clarias* spp (Efe et al., 2024). is consistent with many West African freshwater systems where these species tolerate variable water quality and hydrological regimes. However, such taxonomic breadth also raises conservation and public-health considerations: springs concentrated with humans and livestock are vulnerable to pollution, over-exploitation and human-wildlife conflict (crop/poultry predation by birds or large reptiles) and may conceal shifts in abundance toward tolerant or invasive taxa if water quality declines (Efe et al., 2024). Therefore, the Jikwathlar inventory provides an important baseline for longitudinal monitoring (species presence/absence, relative abundance and seasonal dynamics), and the data should be integrated with water-quality and land-use assessments to guide

local conservation, sustainable use, and community outreach measures.

5.1.2 REGULATING SERVICES

One of the regulating services that is noticeable in the spring area is that the spring environment is a site for natural vegetation decomposition (trunks and leaves). The residents of the area see the spring and its surroundings as a home to spirits that protects and inflict punishments on anyone who defaults on the instructions given by the spirits based on the beliefs that they have from their forefathers. For this reason, cutting down trees in the area is strictly prohibited, and even fallen trees are not to be removed. Instead, they are left to decay naturally at the spot where they fall, no matter how long it takes. The residents use the fallen trees as makeshift lines for drying washed clothes and as seating for resting or socializing (Plate 2). These findings reinforce the analysis of Tee, & Ogwuche (2014), cited in Adeniyi (2021), which states that some communities in Nigeria believe that the forest harbors spirits that protect them from harm and safeguard their families. Therefore, it is considered an abomination to cut down trees or engage in any illegal activities in these areas.

Plate 2: Fallen trees used for drying clothes in the spring area

Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2024

Other than natural vegetation decomposition sites, other regulating services in the spring area includes microclimate and soil nutrient regulations. The practice of plant conservation in Garkida Taula spring environment has

conserved the area mostly in terms of its vegetation. The microclimate coupled with the fertile soil nutrients due to natural decomposition of vegetation within the spring area collectively makes the spring area to have dense vegetation with tall and big trees (Plate 3).

Plate 3: Dense vegetation of Jikwathlar Spring in the Savannah
Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2024

5.1.3 CULTURAL SERVICES

Findings from KII revealed some of the records of cultural and spiritual myths experienced from the spring. The following experiences were narrated by the elders and traditional leaders and the custodians of the community:

- (i) The spirits talk and can be heard, and can give instruction that are audible to the community members. Two recent examples were narrated: A woman once had an issue with her husband and decided to go back to her parents' house, as she was crossing the spring to the other side, she heard a voice that instructed her to go back to her husband as the issue was already taken care of and there

was no point for her to go to her parents. Another story has it that a woman went out to work and was busy for some time without taking care of her baby. The spirits rebuked her saying give your baby breast milk to suck now.

(ii) Sometimes, the sounds that comes out from the area in the evening are likened to children voices when playing. These still exist in the area, up till the time of this interview.

(iii) The myths surrounding the spring help to preserve the morality, resources and also allow the area to go through the natural processes of regeneration. For instance, anything kept within the spring area never gets lost. The community reported that people have died or mad because of immorality acts around the spring.

(iv) Sacred site for sacrifices and a place connecting humans to the realm of the spirits. The community members believe the spirits watching over the spring are also watching

over the community, by protecting the groove and the community at large.

(v) Cordial relationships with neighboring communities. The healing benefits derived by visitors from neighboring communities makes such communities to shower them with favours and grant their requests especially when they seek for wives for their sons.

(vi) The Aquatic species in the spring such as fishes, tortoise, crocodiles, frogs are considered as spirits, hence, they are not hunted, killed or eaten by any one (Plate 4). Hunted aquatic animals would start talking and the offenders will immediately be afflicted with blood flowing out of the eyes, madness, sicknesses or diseases that cannot be cured and even sudden death. It was said that the practices still happen till the time pf this research.

(vii) The community members believe in offering Sacrifices to the spirits for watching over the site, for healing and also in appeasing the spirits incase if anyone temper with the beliefs or even by visitors to the area.

Plate 4: Fishes swimming in Jikwathlar spring
Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2024

The cultural services identified around Jikwathlar Spring underscore its significance as more than just a natural resource, but also as a socio-cultural and spiritual landscape. The site is described as a psychologically refreshing environment that reduces stress and tension, aligning with global evidence on the role of natural spaces in enhancing mental well-being and community resilience (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2005). Beyond its ecological functions, the spring holds deep cultural and spiritual value, serving as a sacred ground for sacrifices, a place believed to be preserved by spirits, and a site connecting humans with the spiritual realm. Such intangible services foster social cohesion, strengthen inter-community relations through shared practices, and sustain indigenous knowledge systems that guide traditional management of the environment. These cultural ecosystem services reflect what Berkes (2012) highlights as the intertwined relationship between local ecological practices, spiritual beliefs, and traditional ecological knowledge, all of which are critical for community identity and sustainable resource governance. Thus, the Jikwathlar Spring is not only ecologically important but also a vital cultural heritage site that reinforces local worldviews, spirituality, and collective well-being.

5.1.4 SUPPORTING SERVICES

The spring environment is endowed with different species of natural of tree plants. Other are crops and fruits planted by the residents around the spring and the surrounding farmland for their socioeconomic gain. These trees and other plant species produce supporting services to the inhabitants inform of livelihood, medicines and food from their roots, fruits, stem or bark. The residents are mostly farmers who engage in farming activities all the year round channeling the

spring water to their farm land without the use of mechanized implements.

They engage mainly in:

- i. Market gardening (both irrigation and rain fed) around the spring
- ii. Subsistence agriculture (both crop production and animal rearing) and
- iii. Commercial food crop farming.

The crops produced in the area are sold mostly at the farm gate to middlemen marketers who in turn take it to Biu or Damboa and are being transported to other places. The following trees, crops and fruits were found within the Spring: Tamarin (*Tamarindus indica*), Mahogany (*Khaya senegalences*), Desert date (*Balaniteaegyptiaca*), Baobab (*Adansonia digitate*), neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Fig (*Ficus carica*), Christ's thorn (*Ziziphus spina-christi*), Jujube, (*Zizizpus mauritania*), Sugar cane (*Saccharum officinarum*), Banana (*Musa sapientum*), Mango (*Mangifera indica*), Lemon (*Citrus aurantifoli*), Sweet potatoes (*Ipomoea batatas*), Cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*), Beans (*Vigna unguiculate*), Pawapaw (*Carca papaya*), Orange (*Citrus sinensis*), Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*), Bitter leaf (*Vernonia amygdalina*), Sorrel (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*), Jute (*Hibiscus cannabinus*), Pepper (*Capsicum annum*), Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus*), Tomatoes (*Salanum lycopersicum*), Garden egg (*Solanum incanum*), Guava (*Psidium guajaya*) and Gutta percha (*Ficus platyphylla*) Other than agricultural practices, the spring water is also used for domestic purposes especially during the dry season when women and children wash their clothes, plates and other related items by the spring sides (Plate 5a & b). Therefore, the community does not experience water scarcity at any period of the year.

Plates 5a & 5b. Residents using the spring water for washing and other domestic chores
Source: Authors' fieldwork, 2024

The supporting ecosystem services around Jikwathlar Spring play a foundational role in maintaining both ecological balance and human livelihoods. The fertile and conducive surroundings for gardening and irrigation highlight the role of the spring in sustaining small-scale agriculture, which is a key livelihood activity for rural communities. Equally important is the wide range of biodiversity the ecosystem supports, providing a reservoir of genetic resources and ecological resilience in line with observations that biodiversity underpins ecosystem stability and productivity (Tilman et al., 2014). Nutrient cycling, facilitated by natural decomposition processes, further enhances soil fertility and ensures the continuous regeneration of ecosystem productivity, thereby sustaining long-term agricultural and ecological functions. These services collectively align with the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005), which identifies supporting services such as soil formation, nutrient cycling, and biodiversity as essential for the delivery of all other ecosystem services. Thus, the Jikwathlar Spring not only supports immediate provisioning and cultural benefits but also underpins the ecological processes necessary for sustainable ecosystem functioning.

6.0 CONCLUSION

The Jikwathlar Spring in Garkida Taula catchment in Biu LGA of Borno State, Nigeria serves as an important ecological, cultural, spiritual, and socioeconomic place not only for the inhabitants but also for the surrounding communities. It provides essential provisioning services such as medicinal plants and a dependable water source for domestic and agricultural use, which are sustainably utilized through indigenous knowledge systems. Regulating services like natural vegetation decomposition, microclimate moderation, and soil nutrient cycling contribute to the area's ecological stability, maintained largely through traditional beliefs that strictly prohibit deforestation and environmental degradation. Cultural and spiritual values deeply rooted in the community view the spring as a sacred site inhabited by spirits, fostering a moral code and environmental stewardship that protect the area from overexploitation. The spring also supports diverse biodiversity and year-round farming activities, significantly enhancing local livelihoods and food security. The integration of spiritual beliefs with ecological practices demonstrates how traditional knowledge can promote

conservation and resilience. Therefore, the Jikwathlar Spring exemplifies the powerful synergy between natural systems and cultural heritage, offering important insights for community-driven environmental management and sustainable development.

7.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

- (i) Policy-makers and conservation agencies should formally recognize and incorporate indigenous practices into local and regional environmental management plans to ensure sustainable resource use.
- (ii) There should be support and scale-up for cultural norms and community-enforced rules to

enhance ecosystem protection while respecting local customs and social structures.

- (iii) There is the need for systematic documentation, validation, and preservation of ethnobotanical knowledge for medicinal plants to safeguard and explore their potentials in broader healthcare applications.
- (iv) To enhance sustainable livelihood and agroecological practices, there is the need to promote water-efficient irrigation, organic farming, and smallholder market access to improve economic resilience without compromising the ecological integrity of the spring area.

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